

Hierarchical Bayesian Modeling of Epistemic Uncertainty in LiDAR Semantic Segmentation

Hanieh Shojaei Miandashti and Claus Brenner

Institute of Cartography and Geoinformatics, Leibniz University Hannover, Germany

{hanieh.shojaei, claus.brenner}@ikg.uni-hannover.de

Abstract—Reliable estimation of epistemic uncertainty is essential for deploying deep learning models in safety-critical applications such as autonomous driving. While common approaches such as Monte Carlo Dropout and Deep Ensembles provide uncertainty estimates by approximating the posterior over model weights, they conflate epistemic and aleatoric uncertainty and rely on expensive sampling-based techniques. In this work, we propose a principled generative approach that explicitly models epistemic uncertainty in the feature space of a deep segmentation network. Building upon GMMSeg, which models class-conditional feature distributions using Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), we extend the framework by placing hierarchical Bayesian priors, specifically, Normal-Inverse-Gamma over the GMM parameters. This allows us to compute posterior distributions over class means and covariances, thereby quantifying epistemic uncertainty in a structured and interpretable manner. Our method enables the generation of pixel-wise epistemic uncertainty maps via entropy over posterior predictive distributions, without requiring multiple network passes or output-level approximations. We demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach in semantic segmentation scenarios, highlighting improved robustness to out-of-distribution inputs and enhanced reliability in uncertainty estimation.

Index Terms—Epistemic uncertainty, LiDAR scene semantic segmentation, Generative classification, Gaussian Mixture Model.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reliable estimation of uncertainty is paramount for the deployment of deep learning models in decision-critical applications such as autonomous driving, where perception systems often depend on robust LiDAR scene understanding. In both image classification and its dense counterpart, semantic segmentation, the prevailing paradigm relies on discriminative models. These models, typically implemented via softmax-based neural networks, learn the conditional distribution $p(\text{class} \mid \text{input})$, effectively mapping input features to class labels by optimizing decision boundaries between classes. Consequently, most existing uncertainty estimation techniques are formulated based on these discriminative classifiers.

While popular uncertainty estimation methods such as MC Dropout and Deep Ensembles estimate uncertainty via repeated stochastic forward passes, they rely on approximate posterior sampling and compute predictive uncertainty based on output variability. However, predictive uncertainty conflates two fundamentally different types: aleatoric uncertainty, which arises from inherent noise or ambiguity in the data and is irreducible with more training data, and epistemic uncertainty, which reflects uncertainty in the model parameters due to limited data and is reducible as more data becomes available.

Separately modeling these uncertainties is crucial, as they serve different purposes in practical applications. Epistemic uncertainty is particularly valuable for out-of-distribution detection and failure prediction, where understanding the model’s knowledge limitations is essential. In contrast, aleatoric uncertainty helps characterize data acquisition noise, such as sensor imprecision in LiDAR systems, and can guide improvements in sensing hardware or preprocessing pipelines.

A common approach to estimating uncertainty in deep learning is to decompose predictive entropy into epistemic and aleatoric components using mutual information between predictions and model parameters. While this strategy is widely adopted in methods such as MC Dropout and Deep Ensembles, it remains an approximation that is highly sensitive to the diversity and quality of posterior samples, and is often confounded by the lack of an explicit noise model in standard discriminative architectures. Furthermore, since mutual information is estimated post hoc from softmax outputs, it fails to offer a structured or interpretable representation of epistemic uncertainty within the model itself.

To address the above-mentioned limitations, we propose a principled alternative based on hierarchical Bayesian modeling, which enables direct quantification of epistemic uncertainty by placing explicit distributions over model parameters. Specifically, we replace the conventional discriminative classifier with a generative classifier based on a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) operating in the latent feature space of a deep network. We place a Gaussian-Inverse Gamma (GIG) prior over the GMM parameters—means and covariances—allowing us to model second-order uncertainty and propagate epistemic uncertainty in a structured and interpretable manner, without relying on sampling-based approximations over output probabilities.

In summary, we build upon the GMMSeg framework [1], which integrates GMM-based generative classifiers into deep semantic segmentation networks, and our main contribution is to extend it by placing conjugate priors over GMM parameters to capture epistemic uncertainty. This formulation enables the explicit modeling of epistemic uncertainty by capturing how uncertainty in the learned parameters of the generative model leads to variability in the classifier’s predictions. Rather than relying on multiple forward passes or output-level variance, we directly infer the epistemic uncertainty from the posterior distribution over the generative model’s parameters, offering an isolated epistemic uncertainty rather than being mixed with aleatoric uncertainty.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. Uncertainty estimation in discriminative classifiers

While some earlier works employ statistics of the model’s outputs, such as softmax probabilities [2] or logits [], Bayesian Neural Networks (BNNs) provide a framework for capturing epistemic uncertainty by modeling a posterior distribution over model parameters. However, exact Bayesian inference in deep networks is intractable, leading to the development of practical approximations such as Monte Carlo Dropout (MC Dropout) [3] and Deep Ensembles [4]. MC Dropout applies dropout at test time and averages multiple stochastic forward passes to estimate uncertainty, while Deep Ensembles rely on independently trained networks with different random initializations. Both methods estimate predictive uncertainty, and epistemic uncertainty is approximated by the mutual information between model predictions and parameters. However, these approaches are computationally intensive, require multiple forward passes during inference, and offer limited interpretability. Moreover, mutual information, while theoretically appealing, depends on the fidelity of the approximated posterior and lacks structural grounding in the model architecture itself.

B. Generative vs. discriminative classifiers

Discriminative and generative classifiers represent two fundamentally different paradigms for solving classification problems. Discriminative classifiers (DCs), such as softmax-based neural networks, directly model the conditional probability $p(\text{class} \mid \text{input})$, optimizing decision boundaries for maximal classification accuracy. While effective in many downstream tasks, DCs do not model the underlying data distribution $p(\text{input} \mid \text{class})$ and often assume class-wise unimodality. This leads to limited expressiveness in representing complex data distributions and often results in poor calibration and overconfident predictions, particularly on out-of-distribution (OOD) inputs. In contrast, generative classifiers (GCs) explicitly model class-conditional likelihoods or the joint distribution $p(\mathbf{x}, y)$. GCs, such as those based on Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), allow for multimodal density modeling, addressing a key limitation of discriminative models. Although GCs have historically faced challenges in scaling to high-dimensional, complex tasks, recent works in integrating them with deep representations have renewed interest in their application for robust and trustworthy learning.

GMMSeg is a novel semantic segmentation model that combines both generative and discriminative approaches. Unlike traditional discriminative classifiers that focus on $p(\text{class} \mid \text{pixel feature})$, GMMSeg employs a dense generative classifier for the joint distribution $p(\text{pixel feature}, \text{class})$. For each class, GMMSeg constructs Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) using Expectation-Maximization (EM) to effectively capture the class-conditional densities ($p(\text{pixel feature} \mid \text{class})$). Concurrently, the underlying deep dense representation is trained end-to-end in a discriminative manner, optimizing $p(\text{class} \mid \text{pixel feature})$. This hybrid architecture allows GMMSeg to leverage the strengths of both generative

and discriminative models, enhancing its ability to handle out-of-distribution data while achieving strong performance on closed-set datasets.

C. Generative Modeling and Feature-Space Uncertainty

To improve interpretability and benefit richer internal representations, recent approaches have explored estimating uncertainty in the feature space of deep networks. For instance, [5] proposed using Mahalanobis distance in feature space to detect out-of-distribution (OOD) inputs. Others have employed Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) to model class-conditional densities and use likelihood scores or distance metrics as proxies for uncertainty [6], [7]. While these methods benefit from structured representations, they typically treat GMM parameters as point estimates, thereby ignoring the uncertainty in parameter estimation itself—especially problematic in cases of limited or imbalanced data.

D. Hierarchical Bayesian Models for Second-Order Uncertainty

Hierarchical Bayesian models offer a natural and principled mechanism for capturing second-order uncertainty, i.e., uncertainty over the model parameters themselves. In classical probabilistic modeling, distributions such as the Gaussian-Inverse Gamma (or its multivariate extension with the Wishart prior) are used as conjugate priors for Gaussian likelihoods with unknown mean and variance [8]. However, their integration into deep learning frameworks for uncertainty quantification remains underexplored. Notably, [9] propose evidential deep learning, which models prediction uncertainty via Dirichlet distributions but remains limited to classification logits rather than structured feature representations.

Motivated by these inherent advantages, this paper proposes leveraging generative models for epistemic uncertainty estimation, moving beyond the limitations of existing discriminative approaches. Specifically, our work focuses on GMMSeg, a novel framework for semantic segmentation that reformulates the task from a dense generative classification viewpoint. GMMSeg utilizes Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) to estimate class-conditional feature densities $p(\text{pixel feature} \mid \text{class})$, coupled with an end-to-end discriminative learning of the deep feature extractor. This hybrid training strategy allows GMMSeg to effectively approximate data distributions while retaining strong discriminative performance. We demonstrate that by embracing the generative paradigm, GMMSeg can provide more reliable uncertainty estimates and robustly handle out-of-distribution scenarios without additional architectural changes or re-training. Our approach provides promising results on both closed-set and open-world large-scale settings using a single model instance.

In contrast to prior works, our method brings together the strengths of generative modeling and hierarchical Bayesian inference by placing a Gaussian-Inverse Gamma prior over the parameters of a GMM in the latent feature space of a deep neural network. This allows us to capture epistemic uncertainty in a structured and interpretable manner, without relying on sampling-based approximations or post hoc output analysis.

By modeling uncertainty directly in parameter space, our approach enables fine-grained reasoning about model confidence and improves robustness in scenarios with distributional shift or limited training data.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section presents our methodology for estimating epistemic uncertainty by modeling distributions over Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) parameters in the feature space of a deep learning model for semantic segmentation. Rather than relying on discriminative classifiers and post-hoc uncertainty approximations, we adopt a hierarchical Bayesian approach to directly quantify second-order (epistemic) uncertainty over the parameters of a generative model.

We build upon the GMMSeg framework [1], which models the class-conditional distributions of pixel-wise deep features using Gaussian Mixture Models. Specifically, GMM-Seg constructs a GMM for each semantic class, where the mixture components are fitted using the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm to maximize the likelihood of the feature embeddings conditioned on the class label. This enables the model to represent the class-conditional density $p(\text{pixel feature} \mid \text{class})$, capturing the statistical structure of features associated with each class.

In parallel, the underlying deep network responsible for generating dense feature representations is trained end-to-end in a discriminative manner. This component is optimized to maximize the posterior probability $p(\text{class} \mid \text{pixel feature})$, akin to conventional discriminative models, thereby ensuring that the learned features are both semantically meaningful and well-separated in feature space.

Our generative classifier follows the core idea of GMMSeg by using the high-dimensional feature space of a deep segmentation model, where features within each class are assumed to follow a Gaussian distribution with class-specific mean and covariance. To quantify epistemic uncertainty, we extend this setup by placing conjugate prior distributions over the mean and covariance parameters of each Gaussian component and updating these distributions in a Bayesian manner.

In practice, for computational efficiency, the covariance matrix can be assumed diagonal, reducing each component to a product of univariate Gaussians. This simplification significantly reduces the computational overhead associated with posterior updates and sampling. However, when modeling richer intra-class variability is necessary, the full multivariate GMM formulation can be retained.

A. Bayesian Inference for Mean and Variance

When inferring both the mean (μ) and variance (σ^2) of a Gaussian distribution from data, it is crucial to treat them jointly because observations introduce a dependency between these parameters in the posterior distribution. Simply combining separate inference solutions for each parameter is insufficient. To model uncertainty over both the mean μ and variance σ^2 of a univariate Gaussian, we adopt the *Normal-Inverse-Gamma* conjugate prior (equivalently, Normal-Inverse- χ^2 when variance is parameterized directly). Given a set of n

i.i.d. samples $x = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, we compute the sufficient statistics:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i,$$

$$\sigma_{\text{MLE}}^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2.$$

Upon observing the data, the posterior distribution remains a Normal-Inverse-Gamma distribution with updated parameters:

$$\mu_n = \frac{k_0 \mu_0 + n \bar{x}}{k_0 + n}, \quad k_n = k_0 + n, \quad \nu_n = \nu_0 + n,$$

$$\nu_n \tau_n^2 = \nu_0 \tau_0^2 + (n-1) \sigma_{\text{MLE}}^2 + \frac{k_0 n}{k_0 + n} (\bar{x} - \mu_0)^2.$$

This Bayesian update allows for the incorporation of observed data into prior beliefs, and the resulting posterior distribution inherently quantifies the epistemic uncertainty in both μ and σ^2 .

B. Multivariate Extension for GMM Parameters

For modeling the components of a GMM in high-dimensional feature space, each class-conditional component of the GMM is treated as a multivariate Gaussian distribution, with its mean vector μ and covariance matrix Σ governed by the conjugate prior of Normal-Inverse-Wishart (NIW) distribution:

$$\text{N-Inv-}\mathcal{W}(\mu, \Sigma \mid \mu_0, k_0, S_0, \nu_0).$$

Given n deep feature vectors assigned to a component, with

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i, \quad S = \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(x_i - \bar{x})^T,$$

the posterior parameters are updated as:

$$\mu_n = \frac{k_0 \mu_0 + n \bar{x}}{k_0 + n}, \quad k_n = k_0 + n, \quad \nu_n = \nu_0 + n,$$

$$S_n = S_0 + S + \frac{k_0 n}{k_0 + n} (\bar{x} - \mu_0)(\bar{x} - \mu_0)^T.$$

C. Integration with GMMSeg for Semantic Segmentation and epistemic uncertainty quantification

We integrate this Bayesian framework with GMMSeg. While the original GMMSeg relies on point estimates of GMM parameters via maximum likelihood estimation (MLE), we extend it by placing Normal-Inverse-Gamma priors over each class's GMM parameters, assuming a diagonal covariance matrix, thereby capturing uncertainty in both the means and covariances.

This hierarchical Bayesian extension allows us to obtain a posterior distribution over the GMM parameters for each class, from which we can sample during inference to quantify epistemic uncertainty. For a given pixel's feature vector, the variability of predicted class likelihoods across posterior samples translates into an *uncertainty map*, such as pixel-wise predictive entropy, which reflects epistemic uncertainty.

D. Epistemic Uncertainty Estimation for GMM Parameters

In the context of GMMs, each component is modeled as a Gaussian distribution. By applying the Bayesian inference framework—using the Normal-Inverse-Wishart distribution (or Normal-Inverse-Gamma for univariate components) as the conjugate prior for the parameters of each Gaussian—we estimate the uncertainty as a distribution over model parameters rather than point estimates. Specifically, epistemic uncertainty is quantified by drawing samples from the posterior distribution and evaluating entropy over class predictions.

This Bayesian treatment offers several advantages:

- **Capturing Epistemic Uncertainty:** The posterior distributions over GMM parameters directly encode how confident the model is in its learned representations, especially in low-data or ambiguous regions. When training data is scarce, the posterior remains wide, reflecting high epistemic uncertainty. As more data is observed, the model becomes more confident, and the posterior tightens accordingly.
- **Robustness in Predictions:** Unlike Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE), which yields point estimates and can be highly sensitive to data variability, the Bayesian approach integrates over the parameter space. This leads to more robust decision-making. In classification tasks, for instance, variation in posterior samples for μ and Σ can be used to generate uncertainty maps (e.g., entropy maps), offering a richer view of model confidence.

In summary, our proposed methodology consists of:

- 1) **Modeling:** Adopt GMMSeg as the base generative classifier in feature space instead of the softmax layer used in the discriminative models.
- 2) **Defining a prior:** Choosing a Normal-Inverse-Gamma (for univariate) or Normal-Inverse-Wishart (for multivariate) prior for the parameters (μ, σ^2) or (μ, Σ) of each Gaussian component.
- 3) **Observing data:** Collecting samples x_i and computing sufficient statistics such as the sample mean and variance (or scatter matrix).
- 4) **Updating the posterior:** Applying the update rules to compute the posterior distribution parameters.
- 5) **Quantifying uncertainty:** Using the posterior distributions to characterize epistemic uncertainty. This can be visualized by drawing samples from the posterior and evaluating entropy over class predictions.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Experimental Setup

In this work, we focus on estimating epistemic uncertainty in LiDAR semantic segmentation. For training and validation, we utilize the SemanticKITTI [10] dataset, which provides dense point-wise semantic annotations across over 43,000 LiDAR frames captured in diverse driving environments. The dataset includes 20 semantic classes covering both static and dynamic objects. Each LiDAR scan is projected into a 2D tensor of shape $64 \times 1024 \times 5$, where the five input channels correspond to x , y , z , range, and intensity values.

As the backbone feature extractor, we adopt SalsaNext [11], a fully convolutional encoder-decoder architecture designed for real-time LiDAR segmentation. The network maps the input to a 32-dimensional feature space. After training the model, we fit a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) per class using Expectation Maximization (EM). We then approximate epistemic uncertainty by updating the parameters of a Gaussian-Inverse Gamma (GIG) posterior over the GMM components. We draw 20 posterior samples and compute the final prediction as the average over samples, while epistemic uncertainty is quantified by the frequency distribution of predicted classes across samples.

B. Performance Evaluation

To evaluate our proposed method, we conduct two experiments:

a) *Quantitative Benchmarking:* We compute the mean Intersection-over-Union (mIoU) of our final predictions and compare it against three representative baselines: Deep Ensemble [4], MC Dropout [3], and GMMSeg, all of which estimate model uncertainty. Additionally, to evaluate the calibration of our epistemic uncertainty estimates, we report Expected Calibration Error (ECE) and Adaptive Calibration Error (ACE). As shown in Table I, our method achieves higher mIoU and significantly lower calibration errors, indicating improved predictive performance and uncertainty reliability.

TABLE I: Quantitative comparison of mIoU and calibration metrics. Our method achieves the best performance in both segmentation accuracy and uncertainty calibration.

Method	mIoU (%)	ECE (%)	ACE (%)
Ours	56.2	2.3	1.9
Deep Ensemble	54.1	4.8	5.2
MC Dropout	52.8	5.1	5.6
GMMSeg	53.5	4.4	4.7

b) *Evaluation under Distribution Shift:* To assess generalization and robustness, we test the trained model on an unseen LiDAR dataset collected using the same 64-channel vertical resolution but a different sensor brand and recorded in a distinct environment. Figure 1 shows that our method effectively distinguishes in-distribution classes (e.g., street, sidewalk, cars) from out-of-distribution elements (e.g., a van or railway tracks not present during training). In contrast, Deep Ensemble and MC Dropout exhibit elevated and often indiscriminate uncertainty responses, failing to reflect class familiarity accurately.

C. Ablation Study: Sampling Size

Since posterior sampling increases inference time, we perform an ablation study to determine an optimal sample count. Table II presents results for 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 samples. We observe that both segmentation accuracy and uncertainty calibration improve with the number of samples, but the marginal gain diminishes beyond 20. Thus, for a practical trade-off between performance and computational cost, we adopt 20 samples as a default hyperparameter.

Fig. 1: Prediction under distribution shift with our proposed approach. IT highlights the parts which has not included during training, while in street and sidewalk it reflects less epistemic uncertainty.

TABLE II: Ablation study on the number of posterior samples. Accuracy and calibration improve with more samples, but inference time increases. 20 samples provide a good balance.

Samples	mIoU (%)	ECE (%)	ACE (%)	Inference Time (ms)
5	54.3	3.8	3.4	42
10	55.2	3.0	2.5	56
20	56.2	2.3	1.9	82
30	56.3	2.2	1.8	108
40	56.4	2.1	1.7	131
50	56.5	2.0	1.6	157

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a hierarchical Bayesian framework for modeling epistemic uncertainty in LiDAR semantic segmentation. Building upon the GMMSeg approach, we introduced conjugate Normal-Inverse-Gamma priors over Gaussian Mixture Model parameters in the feature space of a deep segmentation network. This allows for posterior inference that directly reflects uncertainty in class-conditional distributions, enabling the generation of pixel-wise uncertainty maps without the need for repeated forward passes or ensemble models. Our method achieves competitive segmentation accuracy while offering improved uncertainty calibration and robustness under distribution shift. The results demonstrate the advantages of structured generative modeling for uncertainty-aware perception in safety-critical domains such as autonomous driving.

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